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ICT, young people and social work: distances and opportunities.

Abstract:

The relationship between social work and Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) is an awkward one in Spanish tradition, particularly from a social work perspective due to a certain lack of institutional and professional competence in terms of understanding the capabilities of ICTs. Young people use ICTs to connect to each other and express themselves, however. ICTs represent a means – increasingly the main one – for young people to build and communicate their own identities and understand reality.

As with other social sciences, social work suffers from a difficult relationship with young people. Youth is often studied differently and sometimes perceived as a problem that ends when adulthood is reached. In this context, the relationship among ICTs, social work and young people is also a difficult one. But this problem may also be a solution. By adopting a critical ICT approach, social work can create innovative initiatives and frameworks to improve communication between social work practitioners and teachers as with young people and students.

Imagination and empathy will clearly be key to achieving this, in addition to deeper involvement in the use of new software and applications that can offer enhanced communication and build bridges between social workers and young people.

Key Words: social work, new technologies, young people, competences, software.

1. Introduction.

Over the following pages, we provide a general outline of the areas based in the Spanish tradition, in which there is separation between social work, ICTs and young people, but at the same time opportunity for the development of positive links.

This is a particularly pertinent issue in terms of social work and youth, though not from a perspective in which social work perceives youth as a subordinate and problematic reality, but rather as a field of intervention with all the attendant possibilities; something applicable in professional relationships with young people and relationships between young people and universities. ICTs can act as a unifying force and promote a different approach to linking social work and youth, whether the context is professional or academic.

If we consider young people, social work and ICTs together, the contradictions that divide them only increase. Young people make extensive use of ICTs, which represent one of their relational and expressive facets, but do so in a manner that is different from institutional and academic use. For social work, on the other hand, ICTs have not been easily accommodated, particularly in the Latin American and Spanish context where they have been met with fear and mistrust and perceived as a tool that threatens to remove the human element and even oppress professional activity. (see Guillén, 2003; Puñal, 2004; Idareta & Ballester, 2013).

Our task is not merely to provide a descriptive examination of these aspects. Rather, we attempt to establish theoretical proposals or open up the field to a different way of seeing youth from a social work perspective and, at the same time, to the use of some ICTs that can bring social work, young people and of course universities together – and which we all use, whether reluctantly or otherwise.

2. The disengagement of social work: new technologies.

The relationship between ICTs and social work can be understood in the same context as many other professional activities in which technology has ended up involved in and even determining a large proportion of productive processes. The problem is that in this specific case, we are discussing a professional activity that is at the heart of social rights and directly relates with its clients or users (that is,

with the protagonists). It is hence tempting to adopt a distant or mistrusting stance with respect to technology, and particularly to suspect it of weakening or affecting the necessary human aspects of a “social” profession. This risk is greater as the professional activity becomes more institutional or even bureaucratic.

In Spain, as opposed to the English-speaking world, the process of institutionalising social work happened later (though rapidly once it had started). In fact, during the 1980s and 1990s social work was essential in the development of social services, with social workers forming part of public authorities under the recently created social services legislation, which they had participated in developing.

This achievement, described as the “fourth pillar of welfare”¹, placed social workers in a position of public responsibility for the management of the new social services. This had other unwanted consequences, including the abandonment of fields of social intervention that other emerging professions began to appropriate. This process of bureaucratisation somewhat distanced the profession from the protagonists of interventions (the users). Rather than attempts being made to eliminate those distances, attention was (and still is) focused on examining the profession and its professionals instead of users, along the lines of the Spanish-speaking Latin American tradition (such as the “reconceptualization of social work” (Ander-Egg, 1984), very different in terms of its social reality to that which arose and multiplied in Spain. This was driven by English-speaking perspectives, which were already debating the coercive capacity of social work as seen in the contributions of Dominelli, Payne, Dalrymple, Burke and related authors².

This bureaucratisation was also related with a form of organisation of work in which, over time, technologies for recording customer needs and general needs and resources began to be used. However, there was the potential to miss a large proportion of the nuances that define reality, especially when it concerns people (families, groups and communities).

¹ Together with the other three: health, social security and education. These were democratised after the dictatorship but had already been in existence as public services, unlike social services, which were decentralised and placed within the competence of the new territorial or regional authorities and guaranteed, with their numerous limits, by law.

² Furthermore, this may also have been due to a lack of English language skills (De Lucas, Astray, & Sánchez, 2016).

The need for any organisation but particularly a public one to quantify, classify and measure needs appeared to clash with a conception of intervention that saw it (and hence legitimised it) as more sensitive and supposedly more human. And this was the error – particularly when social work is one of the areas in which social innovation has a greater *raison d'être*, including the use of technologies. Denunciations of the “bureaucratisation” of social workers were already common within a few years of the creation of the public social services system (Guillén, 1993; Idareta & Ballester, 2013), and repeated studies of burnout stacked up at professional and academic conferences (Fernández, 2004). It even justified the loss of fields of study and intervention, which were appropriated by social pedagogy, social learning and sociocultural animation (Quintana, 1997; De Lucas, Astray and Sánchez, 2016).

Technology was not the problem. Rather, problems included contradictions between the legal obligations of the social services system and the ethical foundations of social work (particularly as the system became more precarious), a lack of resources, poor working conditions, high responsibility and precarious political support, and alleged loss of direct contact with users. All of this led to situations of emotional exhaustion, lack of accomplishment and depersonalisation (Maslach, 1998). To the foregoing must be added social workers' lack of digital competencies and a social conception of them, both at the outset of social services and in the present day (Alonso, 2015). This has become a distant position that extends to teaching and, specifically, to the university environment.

The clearest example has been the Social Services User Information System (*Sistema de Información de Usuarios de Servicios Sociales* or SIUSS³), identified as one of the key parties responsible for the bureaucratisation and depersonalisation of social work in the context of social services. It has been claimed that the SIUSS dissolved the essential functions of social (Puñal, 2004) and psychosocial interventions (Gil, 1996). Guillén (1993) heavily criticised the SIUSS, and Puñal (2004) even recalled Mary Richmond in her defence of direct

³ SIUSS was fully implanted in the social services Spanish system since 1994. It is similar to other European computing tools that allows the collection of basic user data of the Primary Care social services, information necessary to perform a professional intervention in response to a social demand. It is configured through family records and allows social workers to manage it. It is accessible in: https://www.mscbs.gob.es/ssi/familiasInfancia/ServiciosSociales/Siuss/DGF_SIUSS_HTML5/index.html

contact with people (though Richmond also pointed to the usefulness of telephones as a practice tool).

In summary, the SIUSS represented a disposition or worldview closer to this distant approach that had come from certain social workers who, although they had acquired higher professional status, remained within a precarious system that suffered from a certain lack of digital competencies and above all participation, ignoring that previous experience and perceived ease of use are fundamental for a friendlier approach to technology (Alonso, 2015).

3. The disengagement of social work: young people.

The disengagement of the profession is not only relevant to ICTs: it has also occurred with relation to young people. But it would be unfair to focus only on social work when this position or approach to youth is a trademark of social sciences.

Social sciences have traditionally taken a hierarchical approach with young men and women, for various reasons. The first and most common is the tendency to confuse the life process with young people as individuals. But at the same time, a good number of theoretical positions maintain that youth should be controlled. It is also true that others – the smallest number – argue that it is necessary for young people to be heard and even used as a dialectic tool.

In short, there are three varying conceptions of youth. The first position represents youth as a period of waiting for adult life, in which young people are passive subjects in need of education and socialization. The second understands youth as an agent of generational rupture, of a counterculture that drives new forms of knowledge and creation. The third maintains that youth could be a corollary or synthesis of the preceding dyad, for which reason young people can be studied based on their achievements and meanings (Romaní & Planas, 2010). As one might suspect, the first position – integrationist or adultocratic (Casal, Merino & García, 2011)– is dominant and, in the case of social work, leads to the selection of controlling, hierarchical and even oppressive or discriminatory approaches (De Lucas, Astray, & Sánchez, 2016).

Many studies and programmes about and for young people are produced on the basis of this posture. For example, numerous studies are focused on deviant behaviour among young people as victims, consumers or wrongdoers living in an at-risk environment (Smith, 2002; Clemente & López, 2016). This perspective

avoids the view that conflict, risk, and even fear form part of processes of maturing and social learning as a form of adaptation and even of social integration (Romaní & Planas, 2010). Moreover, there is an assumption here that deviant and antisocial conducts are the result of individual decisions.

Nevertheless, there are studies with other scope, where young people are not a problem and even, they are protagonists. It is common to fail in any project with adolescents when they feel obligated, but they succeed when they participate in a situation of parity, deciding and scheduling steps to take. Their narratives turn into constructions of meaning and they give full meaning to the construction of their reality (Del Fresno & Segado, 2012). But even when there are approaches to young people related to conflicts as offenses, we can find young people being listened and participating in the decisions of their own lives, despite some of these studies are still focused in individual positions (Navarro, J. J.; Botija, M.; Carbonell, A., 2016). But this is rarer, and the trend is to talk, research and discuss on young people as in a subordinate and conflicting position, especially in the school, place where to reproduce and reify a dependent socialization (Clemente & López, 2016; Castro & Pérez, 2017).

This maybe is because this analytical stance is simpler to use. It comes from the field of public health, where the biology-centric perspectives are really strong and trend to limit social factors by standardising risk factors with the aim of measuring them. The patriarchal and hierarchical society, and more precisely the education system, predominant during the XX century gave the adequate background culture to frame these perspectives and make their application more intuitive. Young people also suffer from similar treatment when their risk and protection factors are studied. The adultocratic scope focuses attention on an individual level, decontextualizing the risk from other juvenile experiences (bearing in mind that young people also undergo other non-risk experiences that are undervalued or ignored due to this fixation on risk). At the same time, the focus is unquestioningly placed on individualised intervention and minimising a particular form of conduct (damage limitation programmes). Young people end up suffering from a stereotyped and exaggerated definition that leads to platitudes regarding unemployment, *ninis* (the Spanish term for those who neither work nor study), school failure and dropout and other problems that are not the result of age, but rather of inequality of opportunity (Martínez, 2013).

Over six years ago, Astray and Sánchez (2012) published work regarding scientific production since 1977 in relation to social work with young people (using the Social Work Abstracts database) and showed that the most commonly used description was “children and families/child and family wellbeing” (a pattern that has been maintained). This revealed the lack of visibility that young people have for social work. In contrast, there is a high frequency of descriptors that refer to typical problems faced by young people (especially mental health and issues relating to their common areas of coexistence (education and school)).

The majority of studies are focused on psychotherapeutic and clinical approaches, to the detriment of group and community work. Examined in more depth, a majority of research is supported by individualistic approaches (psychology and social psychology), rather than social, symbolic and/or cultural aspects (sociology and anthropology).

Young people were in fact one of the historic concerns of social work, in the context of the transformations experienced as a result of industrial development (Coussée, Verschelden, Van de Walle, Mędlińska, & Williamson, 2010). Fields studied included protection against vandalism, the appropriate use of free time, the organisation of mutual support in a context of poverty, moral reinforcement and even the socialisation and education of younger people in terms of academic values, especially as regards immigrants (and particularly in the United States). The Sunday schools of the late 18th century and the youth, religious and later political associations of the 19th century were joined by settlement houses such as Hull House and movements such as the boy scouts and girl guides (Astray & Sánchez, 2012), providing the roots of social work with young people that rather than growing in a clear and specific form, started to become separated.

Individualist approaches began to dominate the social work literature related to this topic. With the professionalisation of working with young people entailing an individualistic, therapeutic and rehabilitative approach, relegating youth participation almost from the outset of the process. Put simply, this informal participation had no place in a context of professionalisation, specialisation and organisation of intervention methods, for which reason young people began to be part of the past, or working with young people became an activity to resolve some of their problems or redirect their troublesome behaviours as users of social services (Jeffs & Smith, 1999). Young people ceased to participate with freedom

in the social work context and were required to do so in obligatory fashion, removing their capacity for mutual support based on similarity and self-identification and on their feelings of community or belonging to an unstructured peer group (Romaní & Planas, 2010).

The outcome makes it very difficult in social work to identify its professionals with social work for young people (Coussée, 2008). One speaks not of social workers with youths (as one would with respect to minors and adults), but rather of situations of risk or conflict: drug dependency, delinquency, and social exclusion. This social work is ever less accessible for young people (Verschelden, 2014) and becomes relegated to a generic form of work carried out with young people via various perspectives and by different professionals, such as police, teachers or sport coaches (Banks, 2010). What is more, this generalist form of social work is fundamentally aimed at young people without special problems of adaptation, who are fundamentally from the middle and upper social strata. In this case, there is indeed an emphasis on voluntariness and initiatives from young people, but subject to an individualist and functionalist perspective of youth that understands this period of life as a kind of waiting room for adult life for young people that do not pose any problems. This is a social work for young people that works but is not accessible. In contrast, the accessible form is that which does not work (Coussée, 2010, p. 12).

In sum, the relation between the social work profession with youth and with ICT needs to be reframed taking in consideration new theoretical approaches that lead to practices that allows new, less adultocratic and distant relations. Also there must be assumed that working with youth people involves more and more a professional sound use and knowledge of ICT. Moreover, all these conflicts are present in the academic space where young people, ICT and knowledge productions meets. Then, is a privileged place to explore new opportunities to change how social work relates with youth and ICT because if students concerns and their use of ICT are hierarchically related, it is no surprise that these three factors – social work, ICTs and young people – reproduce through university itself ways to solve problems that increase these distances.

4. New technologies and youth. Different levels of new technologies: young people and university.

It is nothing new to argue that ICTs are potentially important in professional practice (Perron, Taylor, Glass, & Margerum-Leys, 2010). Moreover, we have even seen that in recent years, at least in Spain, there has been a movement from a standpoint of reticence toward one of demanding ICTs (Alonso, Alonso & Arias, 2016), especially among students who consider ICT as a relevant aspect of their profession. Finding new ways to relate requires a critical background and it hence appears necessary to answer a series of questions relating to the various levels of the complex relationship among ICTs, social work and youth.

The path described with respect to the implementation of ICTs in social work as *disengagement*, and subsequent *suspicion*, at their supposed contribution to professional bureaucratisation has significant similarities to the predominant way in which technologies become established in society. This is what Morozov explains through the concept of “*solutionism*”, or the superficial will to improve the existing state of affairs by reformulating:

all complex social situations either as neatly defined problems with definite, computable solutions or as transparent and self-evident processes that can be easily optimized—if only the right algorithms are in place! —this quest is likely to have unexpected consequences that could eventually cause more damage than the problems they seek to address. (Morozov, 2013, p. 19).

This approach relates to the *will to improve* using ICTs, which becomes the means through which social relationships are articulated, giving *pure* technical solutions that seems to solve social issues in a self-evident way. In other words, it is not solely a question of the predominant way of using ICTs. It is about a specific way of putting professionals apart from the design of these tools that, in the case of social work and youth, has met little success (Chan, 2018). It is not our intention to question the role of computer scientists, however; rather, to demonstrate a manifest disengagement. Moreover, the solutionist approach implies a passive role with respect to the use of ICTs, particularly when the tools that tend to be used professionally raise a dual problem.

The ICT training that students require and which is offered in educational centres tends to reproduce the sense of a passive user, or an individual learning to *use*

technological devices (for the most part imposed)⁴. Moreover, the ICTs that are implemented in the professional sphere reproduce this passivity and on many occasions are removed from the tools that the young population commonly uses. We hence find that the way of educating future social work professionals – young people – and the way in which social work professionally communicates with these young people are unsuitable and highly inefficient. This is particularly so if we consider the processing of information. If we observe the evolution of communication via devices and software over recent decades, there is a clash with the principles of the profession. Young people mainly and often exclusively communicate via messaging networks such as Whatsapp, Facebook Messenger and Instagram, where the confidentiality of data is constantly under threat. In other words, if we wish to use the channels that young people prefer and at the same time to respect professional standards of privacy and confidentiality, we have a problem in terms of privacy and data protection (Reamer, 2013).

The ICT tools used in the educational environment (and also in the social work profession) are probably improvable and in need of update, but their usefulness is undeniable. However, it is a professional usefulness. Students and young people do not use them – or if they do, it is on a compulsory basis in most cases (Alonso Puelles et al., 2017). For example, the Moodle platform for study of the subject and online training platforms in general are almost entirely unused by young people (Alonso, 2015). There is hence a reproduction of the disengagement between social work and youth in university training with relation to the use of ICTs.

This is clearly an undesirable situation, which unfortunately arises from a paternalistic stance in relation to youth, rather than considering how to efficiently train students on use and active agency vis-à-vis ICTs while at the same time adopting new approaches to the relationship between professionals and young users.

Following this line of reasoning in the context of teaching, there is an opportunity for teachers to make use of the immense capacity that young people have in the personal use of ICTs (Alonso, 2015) and to redirect it toward the professional sphere. Put differently, it is a question of offering students the various frameworks

⁴ With this assumption we are not saying that good examples or initiatives don't exist. The scope of this paper is more wider and seeks to underline a general state of affairs.

and tools that will enable them to understand the use of technologies from a critical perspective, so that they can play an active role in their design and implementation, and not merely in their use. This approach involves abandoning the aforementioned paternalism and, together with young people, thinking of new resources and technologies that allow them to develop their potential for critical and reflective thought, without relegating them to secondary roles. In short, the objective is to find a critical framework that turns disengagement into opportunity and enables us to develop competencies in future social work professionals so they can handle a working system (including ICTs) that must necessarily change with their participation.

5. Disengagement offering opportunities. ICTs as opportunity.

Disengagement and differences act as mirrors reflecting opposing stances. These dichotomies can help to give rise to a synthesis in the form of solutions. For example, the more horizontal alternatives – such as learning communities (Garrison y Kanuka 2004; Elboj, Puigdellivol, Soler y Valls, 2006; Wenger, 2010) – are well known in the field of education. Regardless of scope and results, they clearly express that the need young people have is to be able to participate in decisions and proposals regarding how they are educated and study. It is not the case that young people's proposals may be better simply because they are young; rather, they should be taken into account and not seen as a group "in waiting" for adulthood, when they can join those who know what is best for them. Therefore, this different use of ICT between personal (young people, students, young users) and professional (teachers and social workers) use clearly indicate some disengagement. But also shows trends and lines for improvement.

The foregoing diagnosis raises a fundamental problem when proposals are being developed. One of the prominent characteristics of solutionism is its capacity to provide computable solutions or transparent and self-evident processes that can be easily optimised (Morozov, 2013, p. 19). This is undeniably the predominant route due to its high efficiency and, above all, because it allows for measurement and standardisation in administratively controllable processes.

However, we should recognise that we are discussing solutions for problems that were not raised on these terms, which creates an unending cycle of new problems (Alonso, 2013) and, in turn, pushes the social potential for change and innovation to secondary and passive positions. There is not a simple solution, in

sum, meaning the challenge lies in finding an applicable framework that permits the examination of problems in all their dimensions and the provision of solutions that enact active agencies of action.

Illich (2011) proposes a solution based on *coexistence* or a framework for reflection and action that enables disengagements to be turned into potentialities. More than proposing a theory with respect to ICTs, Illich explains a series of criteria to identify when the tool ceases to be useful for people and people become useful for the tool. One may construe this as a new way of perceiving how humans are restricted by what they create.

It is for this reason that it is a priority to engage in ongoing reflection on types of agency and control over tools, their use and the coherence of said use with the purpose for which they were intended. Seen in this light, the coexistence framework proposes a kind of social innovation that is responsible vis-à-vis the real problems faced – in this specific case – by the social work profession, and not a search for solutions based on the range of tools that are available and imposed according to remote administrative criteria. As such, disengagement and differences act as mirrors that reflect a range of opportunities. These theoretical dichotomies find in *praxis* (Freire, 1973; Roberts, 2015) solutions that may not always be definitive but do enable coexistence. This is the case because an action of this kind entails active agency that does not lose sight of the fact that the tool is the means to the end.

Taking into account that a significant proportion of students have greater knowledge of ICTs than do teachers or professionals (Alonso, 2015; Alonso Puelles et al., 2017), a basic coexistence criterion would be to establish more layered communication and work pathways, including ideas and agency from students. For example, more horizontal alternatives are well known within the field of innovative education (Alonso Puelles et al., 2017). These experiences show the need to include young people in processes involving the production of proposals and decision-making regarding suitable education and communication tools. Of course, young people's proposals are not better simply because they come from them; rather, they should be taken into account as active agents and not seen as a group "waiting" for adulthood, when they can join those who know what is best for them.

Together with opportunities, it is essential to accord the notion of experimentation a broader and more prominent role given its fundamental importance in social innovation processes. This is particularly true for Latin American communities, which can be intolerant of failure and errors. Being active agents of social change means that errors will be committed, but they will be resolved taking into account the criteria and ends pursued and not based on administrative settings and control criteria. Nor does there need to be a constant search for provisional technical adjustments; rather, increasingly inclusive solutions should be pursued. In this regard, the possibility of experimentation is an indispensable requirement for inclusive and coexistence-based innovation.

Taking into account a solutionist reality in which active agency is discouraged, and in a context of ICT use that is removed from the principles of social work, relevant training is a priority for undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral programmes. This training, appropriately defined with coexistence-based and horizontal social innovation criteria, will produce professionals with competencies and skills (based on their own strengths) to actively manage and not be passive subjects of ICTs. As a result, it will incentivise the changes and transformations that are required for professional practice to develop more effective communication and a better relationship between social work and youth. In this scenario, ICTs represent a support for timely changes. We know this is not a panacea or a key to liberation, of course, but neither a superstructure congruent with an oppressive system.

6. Conclusions.

At least in the Spanish case, there have been problems for social work in relation to the use of ICTs by professionals who have barely participated in their design and, at the same time, have low levels of competencies when using them. It is not surprising that the relationship between social work professionals and ICTs and with the institutional structure of social work appears to be hierarchical and, to a certain extent, oppressive.

But the relationship between social work and one of its fields of intervention, youth, also reproduces a partial, hierarchical and consequently paternalistic perspective that is a trademark of Social Sciences as a whole.

At the same time, in their studies and training at university (specifically in social work), young people are extensive users of ICTs, taking this use further day to day, making ever-increasing use of them. However, this use does not coincide with the ICTs used to train students, who experience them in a hierarchical fashion and as passive users, as social workers experience ICTs in their work. We hence observe that although these problems are found on different levels, their content is repetitive, amounting to a lack of communication, participation and therefore trust.

In this context, the university can act as a coexistence-based space for experimenting with new ways of designing ICTs that take advantage of the potentialities and creativity of young people to ensure their participation, and to definitively link youth and academia together in a more horizontal and active manner, in direct contrast to adultocratic, passive and hierarchical views.

Moreover, a new theoretical approach that deals with solutionism and offers applied ways to actively solve issues, along with this experience and experimentation can produce suitable conditions for future social workers to also participate in designing the technological tools that are necessary for their work. They will have the experience and habit of participation and will not mistrust the use of technology for thinking that the technology has no social purpose at all, especially if it is imposed upon them.

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